

SKINCARE ONLINE SHOP MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

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Abstract. In today's digital age, personalized skincare recommendations have become increasingly important for consumers seeking tailored products for unique skin types and concerns. The proposed system introduces an innovative Skincare Online Shop and Recommendation Management System that enhances the user experience by providing streamlined shopping processes. The main objective of the system is to manage product information and offer personalized recommendations more effectively and accurately than traditional methods. This system can be an effective, efficient, and enjoyable shopping experience for both customers and administrators.

Keyword: Skin types, Skin solution, Recommendation system

INTRODUCTION

Numerous individuals today are experiencing many skin infections like skin break out, rashes, hypersensitivity and so on. They unknowingly use the items that appeared in ads or suggested by others without realizing their right skin type and what suits them. Clean and healthy skin is desirable for practically all individuals currently. Looking at this fact and watching people make irrational decisions about their skin firsthand has shown the need for a recommendation system, which recommends the skincare product according to the user's skin type. With so many brands claiming to change your skin, it can be difficult to know which ones are right for you. The irony is that all the necessary material is available on the back of each product: the ingredient list. However, unless you have a background in chemistry, it is difficult to read such ingredient lists.

PROBLEM

Traditional skincare shopping methods can be inefficient and cumbersome. In a traditional skincare shop, if customers want to find products suited to their skin type, it is not easy and requires considerable effort. Additionally, if customers forget which products they have tried before, they have to consult with the staff again, which is time-consuming and inconvenient. The proposed system has a problem: the inability to implement an accurate count of available stock in real-time due to potential security concerns and system limitations. This could lead to discrepancies between the displayed product availability and the actual stock, affecting customer satisfaction.

APPROACH

This system consists of two main components: customer and admin. Customers benefit from an intuitive interface that allows them to easily browse products, receive personalized

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recommendations, and track their orders. For administrator, the system facilitates the management of product information, the process of orders, and making it easier to oversee operations. Administrators can efficiently update product details, manage promotions, and monitor sales performance, which streamlines their workload and enhances productivity. Visitors can view home page of the system, test skin type, view recommendation products, view contact details and send message. When they want to buy the products, they need to login. If users already have user account, they can login to the system for buying the products. If users don't have user account, they need to register the account first. After the user's login, users can view product details and buy products that match their skin and add or delete products to wishlist and cart. And also, they can give reviews and can search the products that they want to buy or want to know about the specifications of that product. Users can also update their profiles.

On the administrator side, the proposed Skincare Online Shop System offers significant convenience for administrators. The administrator must login first. After logging in, the administrators can efficiently update product details, view user lists, manage reviews, manage order and manage contact details which streamlines their workload and enhances productivity. By implementing this system, the online shop achieves high accuracy in product recommendations and effective performance in inventory management, all within rapid processing.

Figure 1: System Flow Diagram

Figure 2: Database Design

An Entity Relationship Diagram uses data modeling techniques that can help define business processes and serve as the foundation for a relational database. An ERD attribute can be denoted as a primary key, which identifies a unique attribute, or a foreign key, which can be assigned to multiple attributes. A cardinality notation can then define the attributes of the relationship between the entities. An ER diagram also known as Entity Relationship diagram is a data modelling technique that illustrates an information of system’s entities and their relationships. The database system of Skincare Online Shop System includes nine tables such as user, brands, product, cart, wishlist, orders, confirm_product, payment and review. The figure 2 shows database design for all the data tables and their relationship of the database.

RESULTS

The proposed Skincare Online Shop and Recommendation System offers significant convenience for both customers and administrators. For administrators, the system facilitates the management of product information, the process of orders, and making it easier to oversee operations. Administrators can efficiently update product details, manage promotions, and

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monitor sales performance, which streamlines their workload and enhances productivity. Customers benefit from an intuitive interface that allows them to easily browse products, receive personalized recommendations, and track their orders. They can also access their purchase history and view detailed product information. This system saves time for both customers and administrators by providing a seamless shopping experience and allowing access to information anytime, from anywhere. By implementing this system, the online shop achieves high accuracy in product recommendations and effective performance in inventory management.

Figure 3: Implementation of this system

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the transition from traditional to digital systems has significantly benefited by implementing the proposed Skincare Online Shop and Recommendation System. This project underscores the growing need for innovative solutions that streamline e-commerce processes and enhance the customer experience. As manual methods give way to digital platforms, the system facilitates easier management of product information, personalized recommendations, and order tracking. By automating these aspects, the system improves operational efficiency and customer satisfaction. The Skincare Online Shop and Recommendation System effectively manages product details and customer reviews driving overall performance and scalability for the business.

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